

Mastering Resources for Innovative Solutions in Business: Dissertation Abstract

Abstract

This preprint presents an overview of the author's methodology for identifying and applying resources to develop ideal solutions in business. It outlines the objectives and logic of the approach, the structure of the tools, including the Properties Catalogue and the Business Resources Matrix, as well as the areas of application. The author emphasises the methodological novelty and applicability of the approach to tasks such as developing new products and creating business models.

Structure of the Preprint

1. Relevance and Objectives

Modern business systems are increasingly facing challenges that traditional optimisation methods cannot solve. Ideal solutions are needed—those that achieve goals without losses, contradictions, or excessive costs. Addressing such challenges requires the ability to discover and utilise business resources that companies have not yet fully leveraged.

The goal of this dissertation is to develop, justify, and test a methodology for discovering business resources based on their properties, using TRIZ logic and tools such as Function-Oriented Search (FOS) to enable ideal and innovative solutions.

2. Methodology

The methodology builds on key TRIZ principles, including the concept of ideality, Function-Oriented Search (FOS), resource-oriented thinking, and modelling a system as a set of interrelated functions and properties. Like FOS, the proposed methodology addresses a problem through abstraction. FOS translates the problem into a function and searches for it across industries. The business resources methodology formulates the issue

through a key property required for its solution and then searches for solutions based on that property. Both approaches reject brute-force solution searching and instead apply structural analysis and systemic navigation.

The methodological framework includes six sequential tools:

1. Properties Catalog (*25 universal business properties*)©
2. Business Resources Search Field©
3. Business Resources Matrix©
4. VESC Idealness Filter©
5. Prototype Framework for Proof of Resource-Based Business Ideas©
6. Implementation X-Matrix

3. Novelty

The methodology offers:

- A new interpretation of "resource" in business through properties and functions, not objects
- A universal resource classifier that includes both internal and external opportunities
- Applicability to growth points, Blue Ocean strategies, and resource-based monetisation models

4. Areas of Application

This approach draws on case studies from the medical industry, industrial production, and the hospitality and food service (HoReCa) sector. The methodology helps discover new solutions for tasks such as creating new products, new market niches, and new business models.